

**DIFFERENCES AND SIMILARITIES OF FORMS OF SPEECH IN
ENGLISH AND UZBEK**

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Annotation: *Without any doubt we can say that every language has its own similarities and differences. We can classify languages according to their structure and There are specific challenges to the process of language learning and teaching. Especially if the language being studied is completely different from our native language. In this article, we will try to provide information about the language forms of English and Uzbek. This article will describe some literary and non-literary words and phrases available in English and Uzbek, and compare their similarities and differences between the two languages.*

Keywords: *speech forms , literary form of speech , nonliterary forms, general literary words, poetic words, foreign words, archaic words, obsolete words, communication process.*

Main body. Every language has literary and non-literary forms of the speech. Literary speech is a form of language used in written literature. It is sometimes significantly different from spoken language.

Literary language is the highest form of any language and is characterized by the richness of the vocabulary, the orderliness of grammatical structure, adherence to strict norms, the development of style. The problem of studying literary

language in style is a long one has its roots in ancient philosophy. For example Aristotle believes that human language is social and diverse [1].

If we look at the work of Eastern European and Slavic linguists, we see that the term «literary language» is also used as a synonym for «standard language». The word style is originated from Latin and means "style for writing" [2]. The coloring properties of language are the basis for classifying styles ancient Indian scholars who knew that there are 8, some 10 styles those who put forward the idea [3].

Nonliterary forms of speech is a linguistic style used for informal communication. It is the most common functional style of speech. Idioms and other informal contexts are used commonly in conversation [4]. In addition, nonliterary form of speech includes itself slang, along with abbreviations, contractions, idioms, turns-of-phrase, and other informal words and phrases known to most native speakers of a language or dialect. And also it uses non-specialized terminology and a rapidly changing vocabulary. We can say that the literary words consist of the legal members of the English vocabulary. Because they are not close or dialectal in nature. The literary dictionary consists of the following words and phrases:

1. General literary words
2. Poetic words
3. Foreign words
4. Archaic words
5. Obsolete words

Nonliterary layer words include the following groups of phrases :

1. Common colloquial words
2. Slangs
3. Jargons
4. Professional words
5. Dialect words
6. Vulgar words

Common literary, neutral and common colloquial words refer to the General English Dictionary. Every literary and colloquial language uses neutral words that make up a large part of the English vocabulary. Neutral expressions are the main source of synonymy and polysemy [5]. People always try to speak effectively and expressively in communication. That's why, we always looking for beautiful and colorful words in our communication. And also the words will be customized depending on its functional-semantic nature, or form of speech in the languages. So that we try to use many stylistic devices in our communication process. For example, metaphor, metonymy, irony, epithet, oxymoron and others. Proverbs and sayings serve as the basis of a stylistic device and called an epigram. For instance , we use metaphor –for comparing two objects or ideas by saying one thing IS something else [6].

Nature is the kindest mother – Nature is likened to a Mother, because the properties of a mother like “nursing, caring for” are imposed on the nature [7].

Some examples from Uzbek:

Related to the part of the animals: stolning oyoği, arraning tishi, varrakning dumi, kòchanning boshi, kemanding tumshuği.

Character similarity: shirin sòz, ochiq chehra, oq kòngil, yoruğ yuz.

Similarity of action: arqon ipini uzmoq – òz ma'nosi (primary meaning) — qarzni uzmoq – ko'chma ma'no (secondary meaning) [8].

Metonymy is a figure of speech in which one thing is replaced with a word closely associated with it, for example: 1) Shakespeare's pen is rather sharp, 2) Lisa drinks one more cup. We can see from the examples the relationship between the instrument and action performed with this instrument.

There are examples from Uzbek: auditoriya kuldi – (meaning: people in the auditorium), Navoiyni oldim qòlinga (meaning: the book of Navoiy) .

We can say that the use of stylistic devices in our speech helps us to express our speech more beautifully. Above we have listed some stylistic tools such as

metaphor, metonymy and tried to find examples of them in English as well as Uzbek.

In conclusion, we can face a number of challenges in the process of learning and, of course, teaching any language. Because each language has its own structure, grammatical patterns and forms of speech. Our main task as a teacher is increase our young learners' vocabulary, not only with literary speech words, but also with non-literary words , and teach them how to use language.

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